

Analyzing the localness of OSM data

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A regularly reproduced mantra of the debate on Volunteered Geographic Information (VGI) can be summarized by the term “localness”: it emphasizes the actual or at least the desired local production of geographical information. It is assumed that many “ordinary” people “on the ground” can now generate knowledge about their everyday environment through new tools in Web 2.0. This postulated “local expertise” operates as a claim to truth of VGI. In contrast to “conventional” geographical data, whose truth claim is more likely to be based on professional and technical expertise, VGI is often legitimized by its authenticity due to its “localness” [1, 2].

In fact, relatively little is known about how “local” VGI data actually are. Although “localness” is accepted as a central quality feature of VGI [3], it is hardly taken into account for its evaluation [4]. In contrast, the importance of “localness” is controversially discussed in the OpenStreetMap (OSM) community. Our key interest is therefore to further investigate the significance and relevance of “localness”. We started with a synopsis of all methods that have been already used to measure “localness”. A first insight leads to the observation that many of the used methods work best at regional scale, only some function for a global comparison. Secondly, an examination of the already implemented methods suggests that there are structural differences in the evaluated “local material”. On the one hand, the approaches pursue the goal of determining the geographic origin or “home base” of OSM users (local mappers). This is necessary because this information is not saved within the OSM user data or cannot be read simply from IP addresses [5]. On the other hand, methods seek to find out where the density of local information is high (local content).

Since other scholars mostly concentrate on either of the two concepts, we are most interested in contrasting both approaches. We do so by implementing two methods that work on a global scale – one focusing on “local” mappers and one aiming at identifying “local” content. Using the rather simple method of looking at the first OSM changeset of a user and similar to Neis [6], we examine the “localness” of mappers across the world. Since it is always possible that a new OSM user first has mapped remotely or away from home on a trip, this method can therefore only serve as an approximation of fundamental global inequalities. An advantage of exploring the first changeset is that it can easily be applied globally to all and not exclusively to very active mappers.

To focus on the objects in OSM, we proceed with a method that Zielstra et al. [7] have already applied at a regional level for selected mappers. In order to identify areas with a higher density of local content, we use the framework from Raifer et al. [8] to calculate

multiple indicators on a global level. We determine the ratio of the sum of all used OSM tags to the number of OSM elements per spatial unit. Furthermore, the ratio of the sum of the different OSM keys to the number of OSM elements per spatial unit is computed. It is assumed that a larger number of tags and a greater variability within the keys is most likely to be associated with a higher “localness”.

On a global level, these two approaches thus attempt a data-driven operationalization and approximation of “localness”. Of particular interest is the extent to which local content actually coincides with the distribution of local mappers. Based on the state of research on social inequalities in VGI and OSM, it can be expected that “localness” follows a regional center-periphery and a global north-south divide. However, it is also to be assumed that other phenomena besides “localness” will be observed. For this, a look beyond the users to the OSM objects and their variability is heuristically valuable. An analysis of the tags provides further information about the richness of the OSM data, which indicates the involvement of local knowledge.

Our research could be followed up by a case study on “localness” in a specific regional context. We suggest that both active user groups have to be considered and reference should be made to the OSM object level. In doing so, it is reasonable to dive into exemplary communities in which the contested meaning of local knowledge becomes evident. At the object level, the role of “localness” in relation to the richness and variability of the data could be examined. However, the research conducted so far has provided a more fundamental answer to the question in what way locally produced data in OSM are different to remote data. Being considered as an important indicator for the authenticity of data in OSM, this research helps to gain a better understanding of “localness” in OSM.

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